

IMPACT OF BROKEN HOMES ON PERSONALITY DISORDER AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY ABUJA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: The study examined the impact of broken homes on personality disorder and academic performance of senior secondary school students in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria. Seven research questions and four hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The research employed a correlational survey design. The population comprised 66,390 students in FCT Abuja. The sample was three hundred and eighty four (382) students. A self-design questionnaire was used for the study. The questionnaire was titled: Broken Homes and Personality Disorder Questionnaire (BHPDQ). A reliability coefficient index of 0.76 was obtained using test-retest. The data collected were analyzed using mean scores, standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). The findings showed that there is a significant relationship between broken homes and personality disorder of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria. It also indicates that there is a significant relationship between broken homes and academic performance of senior secondary school also exist. The study further shows that broken homes, personality disorder and academic performance of senior secondary school students are significantly related. Based on their findings it was recommended that counsellors, school psychologists, teachers and school authorities should pay attention to set of students from broken homes for proper counselling and other supportive services, in order to make them focus on their academic activities.

Key Words: Broken homes, Personality disorder, Academic performance, Secondary schools

Introduction

Family remains the primary environment for every child. The impact of family on the success of a child cannot be over emphasized, because family plays a cogent role in the life of a child. The child needs support from the family in order to achieve his aim and be successful in life. In the education of a child, they need the support of the family in terms of getting adequate and necessary working materials in the school, the child needs peace to be physically and emotionally stable so as to concentrate on learning, thereby achieving success academically (Dancel et al. 2019). Family is a basic unit in society, traditionally consisting of two parents rearing their children or a group of individuals living under one roof. The family acts as a socializer and provides vital support financially, socially, emotionally, and educationally. This is in addition to the provision of educational, physiological and psychological needs. A stable family, therefore, is the one which is united, with members

accepting each other's shortcomings, understanding, and appreciating the contribution of each member. A stable home is one in which both parents live together with their children. The level at which the home operates may determine the personality disorder and academic performance of a student in school (Augustina et al. 2018). Also, children that have suffered from neglect or lack of love are known to be psychologically imbalanced to face the realities of life. Chineke et al. (2023) opined that unstable family will not be able to create an enabling environment for the child to do well in his education, as parents spend no time monitoring school work, supervising their children. A child experiencing family instability may not be emotionally stable to concentrate in his studies, just like Again, a child that is brought up in an emotionally tense matrimonial home will not be able to perform well academically because he/she will not concentrate on learning (Abrantes & Casinillo, 2020). This is often accompanied by increase in

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violence, truancy and more negative attitudes towards school. According to Ajila and Akinleke (2012), the home has a great influence on the child's psychological, emotional, social and economic state, and the state of the home affects the individual since the family is the first point of contact as a socializing agent in individual's life. Sheehan et al. (2016) supported the view that children of divorced parents do worse than the children who live with both parents.

Personality disorder is a mental health condition where people have a lifelong pattern of seeing themselves and reacting to others in a way that cause problems. People with personality disorders often have hard time understanding emotions and tolerating distress, and they act impulsively. This makes it hard for them to relate with others, causing serious issues which affects their family life, social activities and academic performance (Bandzeladze, 2020). Students with personality disorder often thinks, feels, behaves or relates to others very differently from the average person. Personality disorder is classified into three clusters associated with anxiety, mood and impulse control and substance abuse. Cluster A personality disorders affect people in different ways. A student with Paranoid Personality Disorder (PPD) are being highly suspicious, will develop strained relations with others. They are likely to experience a depressive disorder, agora-phobia, obsessive-compulsive disorder or alcohol and substance related disorders. Schizoid Personality Disorder (SPD) is characterized by a lack of interest in social relationships. According to Farida and Gupta (2022), withdrawal and or detachment is a characteristic feature of schizoid pathology. Students with this condition may not only have problems with interpersonal relationships but may not be free to interact free in academic activities. Similarly, Schizotypal Personality Disorder (STPD) characterizes individuals as socially isolated and anxious people who may choose to be silent, talk in odd ways or talk to themselves (Fortunato et al. 2022). Evidently, people with STPD find communication difficult with high prospect of learning difficulties.

Researchers in recent times have identified several factors as the major causes of poor academic performance of students. Several studies have shown that broken homes can causes on personality disorder and influence academic performance of senior secondary school students. Mayowa (2021) revealed that family

instability have a great influence on the academic performance of the students. He further stated that parental relationship predict adolescent outcomes in school attendance and academic performance. Nnaoma (2018) found that broken home affects the physical and emotional behaviour and academic life of a child. Students from broken homes finds learning very difficult, most especially his academics activities and these invariably results in maladaptive patterns of behaviour among students. He also pointed out that a crisis ridden home has negative effect on academic performance of their children. Okafor and Egenti (2021) revealed that children who experienced family instability are more likely to show disruptive behaviors in school, and have lower grades and achievement scores compared to children who experienced no misunderstanding. Gidado and Diffang (2023) discovered that young children are sometimes exposed to criminality and other vices as a result of family dysfunction. They further reiterated that children from dysfunctional families do not consistently get their needs met and equally find it difficult to adjust to the larger society, hence some of them resort to diverse antisocial behaviours including exam malpractices, drug usage and abuse. They also engages in a lot of illegal and criminal behaviour to sustain their immediate needs. Maimuna (2018) found that students from broken homes do not perform at their best potentials in school, as they exhibit high antisocial personality disorder behaviour that affect not only their self-concept, social relationships, but can also affect their academic performance. Donahue and Lannutti (2017) affirmed that broken home relationships predicts adolescent outcomes in school attendance and academic performance of school. They further buttress violence at home can shape students' attitudes about school. Simpson (2017) found that adolescents from unstable homes have more emotional problems and low academic performance. He further stress that family and its structure play a great role in children's academic performance. Couprie (2020) found that children from divorced or separated families exhibit lower academic performance in areas such as reading, spelling, and arithmetic. Additionally, these children are more likely to repeat a grade compared to children from households with both parents present. According to Akuta (2017), children raised in single-parent households have worse levels of personality disorder, self-esteem, motivation

for learning and academic performance compared to children living in intact homes with both parents present. Studies have equally shown broken home and personality disorders among secondary school students may hinder the attainment of goals, particularly academic performance. Apeh et al. (2023), show that the consequences of mental disorder in public senior secondary school adolescents includes irregular classes, depression and frustration due to poor academic performance. Gidado et al. (2023) shows that there is a significant relationship between students' personality traits and academic performance of junior secondary school students. They also revealed that personality trait of an individual has significant influence on his behaviour which affects learning habit and skills. Ahad et al. (2023), claimed that personality disorder is the most powerful influence in determining the child's academic achievements. Griggs and Jackson (2017) indicated that students in senior secondary school who came from broken households suffer from personality disorder and poor academic performance. Also, Zubair (2024) shows that students from broken homes tend to feel angry, sad, lonely and many other negative emotions leading to antisocial behaviours and personality disorders, which significantly result in poor academic performance.

Many researchers stress on the importance of students' mental disorder as it directly affect students' learning process. Saikia (2017) stated that the absence of one parent changes the family's decision-making processes and reduces parental control over the teenagers' behaviour and it further argued that single parents give less supervision over their children's socialisation, resulting in personality disorder, poor classroom interactions, cognitive development and academic performance. Sharma (2023) found that children from divorced homes may not be adequately cared for socialised or developed to their full potential. This is because raising a child requires both parents to fulfil complementary tasks as part of the development or socialisation process.

Although various researches pointed above had revealed a certain direction on the issue of broken homes and personality disorder on how it relatively influence student's academic performance. Despite the existing studies, it is clear that the impact of broken homes and personality disorder on academic performance in this

region remains unaddressed and unexplored. This research work, attempts to investigate on the impact of broken homes and personality disorder on academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT-Abuja, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

A family atmosphere of peace, harmony and cohesion strongly influences the overall development of the child, just as an atmosphere of anger and discord has a greater impact on children. The nature of family which a child belongs has a lot of influence on the general life pattern of the child. Therefore, the successful passage through the process of educational attainment is partly dependent on the entire family assistance. Thus ineffectiveness or inadequate family assistance may lead a child to feel overwhelmed, consequently to withdraw from school.

Hence, family stability can be a strong determinant of student's academic performance in school. Family instability can cause parents to become more inconsistent and ineffective in parenting and may reduce responsiveness to children cognitive needs, diminishing the quality of the emotional relationships and attachment between parents and children. This will consequently promote less parental involvement in school work, less or no attention given to early and regular attendance at school and less supervision outside the home. These children are more likely to drop out of school meanwhile disengagement from school is associated with low parental involvement and educational aspirations.

Unstable family has little or no time for parental roles, thus leading to the reductions in the amount of time parents spend monitoring school work, supervising their children and reductions in parent-child communication. This is often accompanied by increase in truancy and more negative attitudes towards school as exhibited by the adolescent virtually from all the write ups and experiences so far gathered, it has come to full knowledge that most parents, teachers, and even the society are ignorant of the role family stability or otherwise play on school attendance and academic performance of secondary school students. It is on this premises the researchers was inspired to investigate on the impact of broken home and personality disorder on academic performance of senior secondary school students FCT-Abuja, Nigeria.

Research

Questions

1. What is the nature of broken homes of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of personality disorder of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria?
3. What is the academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria?
4. What is the relationship between broken homes and personality disorder of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria?
5. What is the relationship between broken homes and academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria?
6. To what extent do personality disorders influence academic performance of senior secondary school students from broken homes?
7. What is the relationship among broken home, personality disorder and academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between broken homes and personality disorder among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between broken homes and academic performance among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between personality disorder and academic performance among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship among broken home, personality disorder and academic performance among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

Methods

Research Design

The study employed a correlational survey research design. Correlation survey design aimed at identifying predictive relationship among two or more variables. According to Cheprasov (2018), a correlation study is a

type of research design where a researcher seeks to understand what kind of relations naturally occurring between two or more variables. The correlation survey design was appropriate for this study because it finds the relationship that exists between two or more variables that are related to one another.

Population of the Study

The population of this study constituted all 66,390 students in public senior secondary schools FCT, Abuja. The total number of public senior secondary schools is fifty-one (51) public senior secondary schools spread across the FCT, Abuja.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample size for this study was 382 students FCT, Abuja. The sample size was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table. Also, proportionate sampling was used to determine the number of students who participated in FCT, Abuja.

Instrumentation

The research instrument for this study was self-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was titled Broken Home and Personality Disorder Questionnaire (BHPDQ). The reliability of the questionnaire was determined by conducting a pilot study with 50 respondents in two schools, but outside the main study area. The first test was administered to the students and re-administered two weeks later to the same students, and the data collected was subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) which yielded reliability index of 0.76.

Responses to the items on the questionnaire was structured using four (4) point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Agree (SD); and Very High Extend (VHE), High Extend (HE), Low Extend (LE) and Very Low Extend (VLE).

Results

Research Question One: What is the nature of broken home of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria?

Table 1: Nature of Broken Home of Senior Secondary School Students

S/No.	Statement	Mean	Std Dev.	Decision
1	I feel unhappy with my family situation	2.86	0.17	Agree
2	I Always feel worried staying with my father only	2.93	0.88	Agree
3	I easily get angry when my friend talk about my family	2.37	0.21	Disagree
4	I still respect my parents even though they are not together	3.14	0.84	Agree
5		2.41	0.35	Disagree

6	I regularly attend and enjoy school events even though my parents are not leaving together	3.31	0.91	Agree
7	I like socializing with others in spite of my family condition	3.00	0.87	Agree
8	Sometime I distance myself from family and friends	3.23	1.09	Agree
9	I lied to cover my family situation from school friends	3.42	0.95	Agree
10	Sometimes I feel depressed because of the separation issue	2.64	0.93	Agree
11	I attempted to commit crime, drink alcohol and smoking cigarettes			
11	I still have a better communication with my parents since they separated	2.55	0.47	Agree
12	I have trust issues relating with others	2.29	0.31	Disagree
13	Sometime I care about my health instead of my family situation	3.31	0.65	Agree
14	I often think about how to solve my family problem			
14	I keep thinking on how my parents will be together again	2.47	0.09	Disagree
15	I always think positive in spite of the situation of my family	2.51	0.95	Agree
16	I am ashamed to share with friends my family situation	3.00	0.91	Agree
17	Despite their separation I still try to strengthen the bond of my family	2.51	0.37	Agree
18	My behaviour changed since the situation of my family happened.	3.22	0.75	Agree
19	I don't have any issue with my studies even if do not leave all my parents	3.31	0.81	Agree
	Sectional Mean/Std. Dev.			
20		3.19	0.89	Agree
		2.88	0.67	Agree

As shown in table 1, the nature of broken home of senior secondary school students in the FCT, Abuja, Nigeria was presented, with a sectional mean of 2.88 and standard deviation of 0.67 out of the 20 items, a total of 16 show agreements while the remaining for show disagreement. This indicates that students expresses the

feeling of depression due to parental separation. However, students tends to be more mindful bout their health rather than worrying about family issues.

Research Question Two: What is the level of personality disorder among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria?

Table 2: Personality Disorder among Senior Secondary School Students

S/No.	Statement	Mean	Std Dev.	Decision
1	I really don't care if I make other people suffer	2.73	0.53	High Extend
2	I always violate the right of others	3.12	0.79	High Extend
3	I am not remorseful for my wrongdoing	2.32	0.42	Low Extend
4	I usually develop strained relationship with others	2.24	0.49	Low Extend
5	I always do things on the spur of the moment	3.30	0.87	High Extend
6	Nothing seems to interest me in school	3.07	0.75	High Extend
7	People told me I always do things in a strange way	3.14	0.63	High Extend
8	I always find it difficult to communicate with others	2.31	0.44	Low Extend
9	I easily get angry	2.43	0.38	Low Extend
10	I have no limit when it comes to doing dangerous things	3.23	0.75	High Extend
11	I lack interest in social relationships	2.37	0.27	Low Extend
12	I hardly concentrate in classroom activities	2.29	0.36	Low Extend
13	Sometimes people describe me as reckless person	3.24	0.88	High Extend
14	I always avoid risky situations	2.41	0.39	Low Extend
15	I always prefer not to get too close to people	3.12	0.86	High Extend

16	I usually get into physical fights	2.59	0.68	High Extend
17	Being rude and unfriendly is a part of who I am	2.18	0.24	Low Extend
18	My emotion sometimes change for no good reason	3.24	0.96	High Extend
19	Other people think my behaviour is questionable	2.51	0.71	High Extend
20	Sometimes I lack empathy	2.88	0.83	High Extend
Sectional Mean/Std. Dev.		2.89	0.61	High Extend

As shown in table 2, analysis of personality disorders among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria was carried out. The table show a grand mean of 2.89, meaning that students exhibit high level of personality disorders. A total of twelve (12) items revealed agreement to a high extent, while eight (8) items

Table 3: Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students

Subject	Gender	N	X	SD
English Language	Male	253	2.73	0.88
	Female	129	2.34	0.62
Mathematics	Male	253	3.13	0.97
	Female	129	2.26	0.53

As shown in table 3, an analysis of academic performance of male and female students was presented. The table revealed that male students has an average mean score of 2.73 with 0.88 SD, while female students average mean score was 2.34, with a standard deviation of 0.62 for English Language. The table further show a male mean score of 3.13 and standard deviation of 0.97

Table 4: Correlational Test between Broken Homes and Personality Disorder

Variables	N	X	SD	r-cal	p-value	Decision
Broken Homes and Personality Disorder	382	2.72	0.61	.808	.000	Rejected

As shown in table 4, a correlational analysis between broken homes and personality disorder was carried out. The table revealed a mean of 2.72, standard deviation of 0.61 and an r value of .808. The table also indicates the p-value of .000 with $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is significant relationship between broken homes and

Table 5: Correlational Test between Broken Homes and Academic Performance

Variables	N	X	SD	r-cal	p-value	Decision
Broken Homes and Academic Performance	382	2.55	0.51	.759	.000	Rejected

As shown in table 5, a correlational analysis between personality disorders and academic performance of senior secondary school students was carried out. The table revealed a mean of 2.55, standard deviation of 0.51

indicated disagreement. The table further shows that students widely exhibit different personality disorders during classroom activities/learning.

Research Question Three: What is the academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT-Abuja, Nigeria?

in Mathematics, compare to their female counter parts who has a mean score of 2.26, with standard deviation of 0.53.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between broken homes and personality disorder among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

personality disorder among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between broken homes and academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

with an r value of .759. The table further revealed p-value of .000, with $p < 0.05$. This means that there is significant relationship between personality disorder and

academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between personality disorder and academic performance among

senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

Table 6: Correlational Test between Personality Disorder and Academic Performance

Variables	N	X̄	SD	r-cal	p-value	Decision
Personality Disorder and Academic Performance	382	2.39	0.74	.891	.000	Rejected

As shown in table 6, a correlational test between personality disorder and academic performance of senior secondary school students was carried out. The table revealed a mean of 2.39, standard deviation of 0.74 and an r value of .891. The table also indicates a p-value of .000, with $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is significant relationship between personality disorder and academic

performance of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship among broken home, personality disorder and academic performance among senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria.

Table 7a: Model Summary for a Multiple Correlational Test among Broken Homes, Personality Disorder and Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria

Model	R	R ² Square	Adjusted R ² Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.859 ^a	.704	.798	.147

As shown in the analysis revealed an R value of .859^a with an R² - value of .704 indicating a high level of influence of broken home and personality disorder on students' academic performance. The adjusted R² Square called the coefficient of determination shows the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. The adjusted R² square value of .798 indicates that 79% of the

variability of dependent variable (academic performance) can be explained on the basis of the independent variables (broken homes and personality disorder).

To further buttress the statistical significance of each of the independent variables, analysis was further carried out and results presented on table 7b.

Table 7b: Table of Coefficients for Test of Broken Homes and Personality Disorder Influence on Students' Academic Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	2.119	.074			29.468	.000
Broken Homes	.274	.049			9.132	.000
Personality Disorder	.033	.068	.736	.305	.735	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

The analysis in the table 7b shows the statistical significance of each independent variable. The results showed that broken homes and personality disorder has a dominant influence on students' academic performance, with p value of .000 and .000 for both

broken homes and personality disorder respectively. Generally, the multiple linear regression shows that academic performance is dominated by broken homes and personality disorder with $F(8.705) = 136.568$, $p < .05$, $R^2 = .704$.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that there is a significant relationship between broken homes and personality disorder of senior secondary school students in the FCT, Abuja. This is in agreement with an earlier finding by Okafor and Egenti (2021) who found that broken home condition adversely affect student's concentration on their studies and regular attendance in school. The study also indicates that broken homes leads to various psychological disorders which mostly affects the mental health and wellbeing of students. This is in agreement with the finding of Sharma (2013) who revealed that significant relationship exist between broken homes and personality disorder of senior secondary school students. The finding also revealed that personality disorder involve long-lasting disruptive patterns of thinking, behaviours and other related issues. The finding is also in line with an earlier finding by Gidado and Diffang (2023) who discovered that young children sometimes exposed to criminality and other vices as a result of family dysfunction. They further reiterated that children from dysfunctional families do not consistently get their needs met and equally find it difficult to adjust to the larger society, hence some of them resort to diverse antisocial behaviours including exam malpractices, drug usage and abuse and also engages in a lot of illegal and criminal behaviour to sustain their immediate needs. The finding is also consistent with the finding of Gidado et al., (2023) on the significance of environment as a key determinant of student's academic achievement, with uncomfortable, unstable home and unpeaceful learning having negative effect on learning skills and academic achievement.

From the study, it was also found that significant relationship exist between broken homes and students' academic performance in the FCT, Abuja. This finding is agrees with the finding of Saikia (2017) which that there is a significant relationship between broken homes and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Baybay City, Leyte Philipines. He pointed out that the side effects of broken home include emotional instability, lateness and absenteeism, aggression, frustration, lower self-esteem, lack of motivation and poor academic performance. The finding is in line with earlier finding by Chineke and Chidiezie-Chineke (2023) which revealed that broken homes contribute negatively to students' academic performance. They also indicated that provision of

accessible and well-resourced counselling services with trained and motivated professionals will support students' social, emotional and psychological wellbeing. The finding further echoed the findings of Fariba and Gupta (2022) who discovered that the emotional and social stress of students from broken homes causes hardship, such as inability to resume classes as at when due, inability to purchase necessary learning materials, nonpayment of dues and levies, lack guidance and counselling, monitoring and supervision, insecurity, lack of freedom from oppression and denial of early education thereby resulting in poor academic performance in school.

On personality disorder and academic performance, the study found that there is a significant relationship. The finding is consistent with the finding of Gidado et al. (2023) shows that there is a significant relationship between students' personality traits and academic performance of junior secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria. They also revealed that personality trait of an individual has significant influence on his behaviour, and can affect learning habits and skills. This finding contradicts an earlier finding by Ahad et al. (2015) which shows that there is no significant correlation between personality disorder and academic achievement. The finding further contradicts earlier finding by Chamorrer-Premuzic and Fumharn (2015) there is no significant relationship between personality disorder and academic achievement of secondary school students. Their findings, like those of Gidado et al. (2023) shows that this is because students who experience unpleasant emotions are easily and negatively affect and display poor performance in school. The finding are also consistent with the findings of Apeh et al. (2023), which shows that the consequences of mental disorder in public schools in FCT includes among other things, poor academic performance. This is consistent with the findings of Sheehan et al. (2016) which supported the view that children from divorced parents do worse than children living with both parents. On the issue of relationships among broken homes, personality disorder and academic performance, the study found that there is a significant relationship, with all variables influencing one another. The finding is consistent with the finding of Johnston (2021) which shows that a significant relationship exist among broken homes, personality disorder and academic achievement

of students. He also suggested that students who exhibit personality disorder tend to exhibit deviant and anti-social behaviour in school, which results in low academic achievement. This is also consistent with the finding of Nnaoma (2018) who found that relationship exist amongst broken homes, personality disorders and academic performance of senior secondary school students. His study further stressed that students from broken homes exhibit high personality disorder as they do not care if other people suffer during classroom learning. However, the finding is at variance with the findings of Sheema et al (2016) which indicated that broken homes and personality disorders among students only enhances learning activities with students exhibiting high learning skills and academic performance. This variation might be the result of different teaching strategies adopted by classroom teachers or largely due to other environmental factors. The effect of differentiated instruction is echoed by Gidado et al (2024), while the relevance of environment in shaping learning outcomes was earlier reiterated by (Gidado, 2000). His study show low parental socio-economic and school environment background has positive impact of children's performance in school in respective of the type of home they are coming from. This finding is also in agreement with the finding of Zubair (2024) which revealed that students from broken homes tend to feel angry, sad and lonely, leading to antisocial behaviours and poor performance. This is further supported by Ibrahim et al's. (2022) study which shows that parental support is significantly related to academic achievement of children. They indicated that parent's financial support for children's education tend to have positive impact on their academic performance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, students from broken homes always expressed the feeling of depression due to parental separation. However, students tend to be more mindful about their health rather than worrying about their family issues. Also, students widely exhibit personality disorders including anti-social behaviour, moody, assaults and disruptive behaviour during and after classroom activities/learning. However, broken homes and personality disorders significantly influence students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings of the research.

1. Counsellors, school psychologists, teachers and school authorities should pay attention to set of students from broken homes for proper counselling and other supportive services, in order to make them focus on their academic activities.
2. Families must inculcate the habit of understanding, tolerance and forgiveness in order to avoid violence home or divorce. This is because violence/divorce in the home has negative effect on the academic performance of their children.
3. Students should also be given sufficient information on personality disorder so that those who may suffer from them are aware and cooperate with counselling departments in seeking the required intervention.
4. Categories of personality disorders as new concept, should be taught to all senior secondary school students as a way of preparing them to meet challenges in their school life and work life.

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